

Raman spectroscopy and PCA, MCR study of heavy weathered glass.

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ABSTRACT

The chemical composition of a glass surface is a key factor in its interaction with the environment. Under certain exposure conditions its optical properties, chemistry and structure are modified by different weathering processes [1]. As a consequence of the interaction between the glass and a solution, irreversible changes in glass can be observed. Most important of them are as follows: dissolution of the glass, transfer of glass components into the solution, changes of glass surface composition, especially the depletion of alkali and alkali earth ions, and creation of secondary precipitated layers on the glass surface [2-3].

The corrosion products on heavy weathered surface of barium crystal glass were studied by the micro Raman spectroscopy. Spectra were recorded in the range of (200–1500) cm^{-1} by RENISHAW inVia Reflex Raman spectrometer with the Leica DM2500 microscope. The excitation 532 nm laser with 28.5 mW power was used for a spot of about 1 mm diameter.

The weathered surface was studied by lateral spectral maps recorded in the autofocus mode. The surface of approximately (0.5 x 0.5) mm was scanned into the map of the size of 12 x 12 points.

The stratified structure of glass weathered surface was studied by Raman spectra depth profiling. The series of Raman spectra were recorded with different focusing depth level ranging from surface level up to the depth of 10 μm .

After the baseline subtraction the number of independent spectral components was determined by the Principal Component Analysis (PCA). Then the spectra of pure components (so called loadings) and their relative abundances (so called scores) were determined by the multivariate curve resolution method (MCR). The corrosion products were identified by the S.T. Japan database applied to each MCR loading. This way the following weathering/corrosion products were identified corrosion products on Table 1 were identified by the micro Raman spectroscopy on the weathered glass surface by the S. T. Japan Spectral database.

Table 1: Corrosion product

	Characterization corrosion products	
ST Japan Spectral databases	St # 931	OKENITE (hydrated calc-silicate) $\text{Ca}_5\text{Si}_9\text{O}_{23} \times 9\text{H}_2\text{O}$
	St # 746	Pyrophyllite (aluminosilicate) $\text{Al}_2\text{Si}_4\text{O}_{10}(\text{OH})_2$
	St # 379	Okenite (hydrated calc-silicate) $\text{Ca}_5\text{Si}_9\text{O}_{23} \cdot 9\text{H}_2\text{O}$
	St # 405	Tridymite (Silica group) SiO_2 (GSJ M35459)
	St # 187	Cordierite $\text{Mg}_2\text{Al}_3(\text{AlSi}_5\text{O}_{18})$

Keywords: Barium crystal glass, PCA, MCR, micro Raman spectroscopy, corrosion products

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